

Numerical and Experimental Evaluation of Structured Material for Use in Multi-scale Topology Optimization

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Abstract:

Multi-scale topology optimization is a powerful tool for engineers seeking a design with minimum weight and maximum stiffness, using a structured material in the form of a lattice structure for the geometric interpretation of the entire range of relative densities. However, the choice of lattice topology is not always a key issue, although it can be very important for the final performance of the design. Therefore, two hypotheses are tested in this study. The first hypothesis states that an additional weight saving of more than 30% can be achieved by a better choice of lattice topology. The second hypothesis is based on the manufacturing limitations of the Laser Powder Bed Fusion technology and the assumption that a favorable loading direction parallel to the building direction exists. The hypotheses are tested numerically and experimentally by compression tests in two directions for six basic lattice topologies. The first hypothesis is confirmed only for loading in the direction parallel to the building direction and the second only for two lattice topologies. When both hypotheses are combined, the additional weight reduction of the multi-scale topology optimization result is 44.5% according to the numerical results and 32.7% according to the experimental verification.

1. Introduction

Topology optimization as a tool to determine the optimal design of components has now been used for a long time, and since the beginning, the material used for the design has been porous.^[1] Such topology optimization that separates the scales and optimizes not only the macro shape but also the structure of the material is called a multi-scale topology optimization.^[2] Methods using structured material were unfortunately purely theoretical at first due to the difficulties and moreover due to the lack of manufacturing capabilities.^[3] With the advent of additive manufacturing in its polymer and, more recently, metal versions, researchers working on multi-scale topology optimization have finally been given a tool to realize their designs.^[4] However, in order to use structured materials in multi-scale topology optimization, it is important to be able to predict their mechanical properties. According to the Gibson-Ashby cellular material theory, the mechanical properties of porous materials depend on the parent material, the relative density, and the geometry of the unit cell.^[5]

An aluminum alloy AlSi10Mg was chosen as the parent material for this study, as it is one of the most used materials in Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) technology. Its high stiffness to weight ratio, high thermal conductivity and stable manufacturing process make AlSi10Mg an ideal candidate for engineering applications in many industries such as automotive or aerospace.^[6,7] Furthermore, researchers agree that AlSi10Mg does not suffer from anisotropy caused by the different build orientation,^[8,9] which is an important advantage for industrial use. Due to the precipitation hardening potential of this alloy and the possibility of adjusting the resulting mechanical properties, extensive research has also been carried out in the field of post-processing heat treatment.^[10-13] Heat treatment for AlSi10Mg can be divided into two groups – annealing to relieve residual stresses and solution annealing followed by precipitation hardening, also known as T6 treatment. Mertens et al. compared these two groups and found that annealing reduces the yield strength, ultimate strength, and hardness, but increases the elongation at break.^[12] On the other hand, solution treatment increases the yield strength and improves the ductility even more than annealing. The comparison was also made by Vaverka et al. who also pointed out the effect on residual stress and the induction of inner compressive stress by water cooling.^[14] T6 heat treatment is used to improve the mechanical properties not only of the bulk material but also of the lattice structures. For example, Megahed et al. investigated different temperatures and holding times.^[15] However, other authors used the T6 treatment as a common method for post-processing the lattice samples, for example Maskery et al. or Wang et al.^[16,17]

The mechanical properties of lattice structures made of AlSi10Mg were investigated in detail. The effect of process parameters was investigated by Fiocchi et al. or Ossola et al. and even special hatching strategies for lattice structures were proposed by Sos et al. or Vrána et al.^[18–21] In the mentioned studies, the main focus is on compressive properties such as compressive strength, energy absorption or impact energy. Other test methods such as tensile, shear or torsion tests have also been investigated, but are less common.^[22] Some researchers also compared different lattice structures to find the best one for the above mentioned properties.^[23,24] Different relative densities, different cell sizes or strut diameters have also been tested.^[25,26]

However, for multi-scale topology optimization, which mostly works in the elastic domain, the stiffness of the lattice structure is the most important property. This property, which is defined by the Young's modulus of elasticity (for bulk material) or the effective modulus of elasticity (for the structure), is usually not the objective of the studies. Researchers assume that the Young's modulus of elasticity remains constant with little change during heat treatment, or they use the conventional tensile specimens to predict the properties of lattice structures.^[18,22,27] However, Dong et al. have shown that the Young's modulus of elasticity varies significantly with the strut diameter or build orientation of the struts.^[28,29]

Since horizontal geometries are not recommended due to the need for supports,^[30] low mechanical properties,^[29] or poor geometric accuracy,^[19] the simplest truss-based lattice structures are geometrically anisotropic (see **Figure 1** in Section 2.1). Despite this fact, the lattice structures in different orientations are only studied for other materials prone to material anisotropy, such as 316L stainless steel,^[31] maraging steel,^[32] and titanium alloy Ti6Al4V,^[33] or only with the means of finite element analyzes.^[34] Therefore, there is an urgent need for such a comparison for the most commonly used aluminum alloy, as multi-scale topology optimization could significantly profit from such insights.

By choosing the lattice topology, the mass saving achieved by multi-scale topology optimization could be pushed even further. In the study by Aremu et al. the authors state that the FCCZ lattice topology is able to withstand twice the loading force than the BCC lattice cell at the same relative density,^[34] conversely, the FCCZ lattice topology could have a lower relative density at the same loading force. Hanzl et al. and Smith et al. also pointed out the importance of struts with their axis parallel to the loading direction.^[32,35]

Based on the literature review, two working hypotheses were established, which are tested in this paper:

1. The result of multi-scale topology optimization can be improved by changing the lattice topology and maintaining the stiffness by an additional 30% weight reduction.
2. The loading of lattice structures in the direction parallel to the build direction is always advantageous as there are no struts parallel to the build plate. Therefore, changing the manufacturing orientation of the part will save additional mass while maintaining stiffness.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Geometry of lattice specimens

In this study, the lattice topologies body-centered cube (BCC), face-centered cube (FCC) and body and face-centered cube (BFCC) as well as their variants with additional struts in the Z-direction – BCCZ, FCCZ and BFCCZ – were investigated (see Figure 1). All lattice specimens were 30 mm cubes consisting of 27 cells with a cell size of 10 mm. The specimens were designed with relative densities of 0.3, 0.4, 0.55 and 0.7. Therefore, each lattice cube had a different strut diameter as shown in **Table 1**.

Figure 1. Topologies of lattice cubes (from left to right: BCC, BCCZ, FCC, FCCZ, BFCC, and BFCCZ).

Table 1. Specimen types with respective strut diameters.

Specimen	Strut diameter [mm]	Specimen	Strut diameter [mm]	Specimen	Strut diameter [mm]
BCC-0.3	2.70	FCC-0.3	3.04	BFCC-0.3	2.03
BCC-0.4	3.22	FCC-0.4	3.64	BFCC-0.4	2.43
BCC-0.55	3.97	FCC-0.55	4.54	BFCC-0.55	3.02
BCC-0.7	4.74	FCC-0.7	5.55	BFCC-0.7	3.67
BCCZ-0.3	2.54	FCCZ-0.3	2.86	BFCCZ-0.3	1.95
BCCZ-0.4	3.03	FCCZ-0.4	3.46	BFCCZ-0.4	2.34
BCCZ-0.55	3.74	FCCZ-0.55	4.41	BFCCZ-0.55	2.91
BCCZ-0.7	4.50	FCCZ-0.7	5.51	BFCCZ-0.7	3.53

Each specimen was fabricated twice – once for testing in the Z-direction and once for testing in the XY-direction. The reason for this is the limited area of a build platform (and the wide range of geometries tested – 48 specimens in total) and an effort to minimize differences between specimens caused by fabrication or post-processing by processing them all at once.

2.1. Production of specimens

All specimens were fabricated from an AlSi10Mg alloy with an SLM 280^{HL} machine (SLM Solutions, Lübeck, Germany) using LPBF technology. The respective cross-sections were produced with a 400 W YLR fiber laser with a spot diameter of 82 μm .

The standard process parameters specified by the manufacturer SLM Solutions were used for the build job, i.e. a laser power of 350 W, a scan speed of 930 mm s^{-1} , a hatch distance of 0.17 μm , a layer thickness of 50 μm , a preheating of the build platform of 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a nitrogen atmosphere with an oxygen concentration below 0.5%. The scanning strategy was standard with one contour and hatch with meander scanning.

According to a previous study, the best combination of mechanical properties was observed with the T6 treatment condition, i.e., solution annealing at 520 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 6 h, followed by water cooling and artificial aging at 175 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h.^[14] The T6 treatment was also applied to unify the microstructure of the lattice specimens and eliminate the anisotropy of the material caused by the non-uniform heat dissipation during fabrication.^[36,37]

2.2. Testing and examination of specimens

The mechanical tests were performed on the Zwick Z250 universal testing machine (Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany) with a load cell of 150 kN. All specimens were tested in compression with a preload of 20 N and a test speed of 1 mm min^{-1} .

From the force range F in the elastic region, the theoretical stress σ_{teor} in the specimens was calculated by dividing it by the total area of the respective cube A ($\approx 900 \text{ mm}^2$ based on the actual area of the respective specimens) (Equation (1)). The real displacement h in the selected force range F was divided by the initial height at the beginning of the interval h_1 and the strain value ε was determined (Equation (2)). The effective modulus of elasticity EM of the lattice specimens was calculated from the stress-strain ratio (Equation (3)).

$$\sigma_{\text{teor}} = \frac{F_2 - F_1}{A}, \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{h}{h_1} = \frac{h_2 - h_1}{h_1}, \quad (2)$$

$$EM = \frac{\sigma_{\text{teor}}}{\varepsilon}. \quad (3)$$

Two fundamental properties were calculated from all experiments and simulations. The effective modulus of elasticity of the structure (EM), which is the effective property of the whole specimen and takes into account the effects of lattice arrangement, manufacturing defects, relative density and parent material. The second property was the Young's modulus of the parent material (YM), which reflects only the state of the material and manufacturing defects and is independent of lattice arrangement or relative density.

2.4. Finite element analyses

Finite element analyses were performed using ANSYS Workbench (Ansys Inc., Canonsburg, Pennsylvania). The compression tests in the linear domain were simulated by two types of analyses using the nominal and parametric material model.

2.4.1. Model of material

The material AlSi10Mg was defined as a linear elastic material in ANSYS Workbench. For the nominal material model, the YM was set to 68.5 GPa, the Poisson's ratio to 0.33 and the density to 2670 kg m^{-3} .

To determine the actual mechanical properties of the parent material, the parametric material model was created using the YM of the parent material as a parameter. This procedure was based on the work of several authors who have shown that the real YM value is different for solid material and lattice structure.^[28,38,39] The YM value was changed until the FEA results matched the experiment – the maximum deviation of the EM was set to 0.5 GPa. The other material properties remained unchanged.

2.4.2. Analysis setup

Due to the simplicity of the calculation and stability, quarter models of lattice specimens were used – the symmetry constraints ensure the position of the specimen in the center and prevent the specimen from moving in the direction perpendicular to the loading direction. Two planes were added to the specimen to represent the loading surfaces of the testing machine (one fixed and one moving plane), which also prevent the specimen from moving in the direction parallel to the loading direction.

The thickness of the loading planes was set to 0.3 mm, and they were assigned the standard structural steel material with a YM 1000 times higher. This approach was used to simulate the several times higher stiffness of the testing machine compared to the lattice specimen. Both planes were meshed with Quad4 (Shell181) elements with a size of 1 mm (not the object of the simulation). The lattice specimens (material AlSi10Mg) were meshed with Tet10 (Solid187) elements with a size of 0.6 mm (at least 3 elements on the thickness of 1.95 mm for the thinnest strut used). For an even higher quality mesh, adaptive meshing was used with increased mesh quality checks.

The bottom plane was fixed in displacement and rotation and a displacement condition was prescribed on the top plane (representing the actual test conditions). A two-step displacement of 0.01 mm (to ensure the linear elasticity region) in the Z- (first group) or Y- (second group) direction was used. The other degrees of freedom were restricted. The contacts between the specimen and the loading planes were specified as frictional with a friction coefficient f of

0.35 (table value for aluminum–steel contact).^[40] An overview of the FEA setup can be found in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Boundary conditions of the FEA for the first group.

From the simulations, the force reactions in the loading surfaces were determined in the first step (displacement of 0.005 mm) and in the second step (displacement of 0.01 mm). The FEA results were processed using Equation (1-3) in the same way as the results of the mechanical tests.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. FEA results with nominal material model

The graph in **Figure 3** shows the *EM* of the respective specimens using the FEA with nominal *YM* for the compression test in the Z-direction (Figure 3a) and XY-direction (Figure 3b). The difference in the maximum values for these two directions is approximately 6.5 GPa (38.1 GPa and 31.6 GPa for FCCZ-0.7). The highest *EM* in both directions and for the entire range of relative densities was achieved by FCCZ, which is consistent with the literature.^[34,41] In the first group (Z-direction, Figure 3a), the highest resulting *EM* belong to the Z-variants of the lattice types. This is obviously due to the Z-struts, which are coaxial to the loading direction, as other authors have also noted.^[32,35] Nevertheless, the FCC is stiffer in the Z-direction than BCCZ and BFCCZ, despite the absence of Z-struts. The reason for this is the different angle of the struts in FCC and BCC. In addition, the BFCC consists of more struts than the FCC and therefore the strut diameter must be smaller for a constant value of the relative density.

In the second group (XY-direction, Figure 3b), the Z-struts do not play a significant role and the *EM* of the basic variants and the variants with the Z-struts are quite similar. The results are

mostly sorted by lattice topology, with FCC and FCCZ having the highest EM values, BFCC and BFCCZ in the middle and BCC and BCCZ at the bottom.

Figure 3. Results of FEA for loading in a) Z-direction, b) XY-direction.

According to the FEA, the mass saving by changing the lattice topology is up to 43% in the Z-direction and 29% in the XY-direction. The same values for EM are valid for the Z-direction for BCC with a relative density of 0.55 and FCCZ with a relative density of about 0.31. For the XY-direction it is BCCZ with a relative density of 0.55 and FCCZ with a relative density of 0.39. The FEA thus confirms the first hypothesis in the Z-direction, but in the XY-direction there is a deviation of 1% (29% compared to the expected 30%).

Figure 4 shows the ratio of EM of the respective load directions. The BCC type is geometrically isotropic, so there is no difference between the load in the XY- and Z-direction. The BFCC type is the only one that is stiffer in the XY-direction than in the Z-direction, although the arrangement of the struts should have an opposite effect. In the BFCCZ type, the advantageous direction changes with the relative density. This change occurs at a relative density of 0.55. For all other specimens, loading in the Z-direction is more favorable for stiffness. Therefore, the second hypothesis is not generally confirmed by the FEA.

Figure 4. Ratio of EM for loading in Z- and XY-direction according to the FEA.

3.2. Experimental testing

The graphs in **Figure 5** show the results of the experimental test in the Z-direction (Figure 5a) and XY-direction (Figure 5b). The first difference between the FEA and experimental results is the range of EM values obtained. The difference ranges from -18% for FCC-0.7 in the Z-direction to -72% for BCCZ-0.3 in the Z-direction. This is likely to be due to the decrease in mechanical properties (especially YM) of the parent material or a general defect caused by manufacturing or post-processing. The second difference is the change in the ranking of lattice topologies in the Z-direction, with FCC being the stiffest at relative densities above 0.3 according to the experimental tests.

The average decrease in EM in the Z-direction is -47%. For all FCC samples, the decrease in EM was less than the average value (from -18% for FCC-0.7 to -45% for FCC-0.3). The other five lattice topologies are mixed, with lower relative density samples performing worse. The highest decrease was achieved by the FCCZ and BFCCZ specimens. All specimens with a relative density of 0.7 show the lowest decrease in EM (below the average value). This indicates a decrease in stiffness for smaller diameter struts, which has also been reported by other authors.^[28,38,39]

On the other hand, Figure 5b, which presents the results of the experimental test in the XY-direction, shows the same ranking as in the case of the FEA. The decrease in EM is also lower, namely -34% on average. Unfortunately, the specimen BFCCZ-0.7 clearly deviates from the normal behavior. At a relative density of 0.7, an even lower EM is achieved than at a relative density of 0.55. This could be due to a local manufacturing error.

Figure 5. Results of experimental testing in a) Z-direction, b) XY-direction.

3.3. FEA results with parametric material model

As mentioned in the Section 3.2, the *EM* of the specimens suffer from very low values, which most likely indicates changes in the parent material. Therefore, the parametric study was performed to determine the true *YM* of the material for each specimen (details in the Section 2.4.1).

Figure 6 shows the relationship between the strut diameter and the resulting *YM* of the parametric material model. Figure 6a shows no correlation between the *YM* and the topology of the specimen, i.e. the presence of additional Z-struts has no global influence. However, when the legend of the graph is sorted according to the loading direction, as shown in Figure 6b, a strong dependency is clearly visible. The *YM* for the specimens loaded in the XY-direction is in the range of 41 to 54 GPa and decreases slightly with increasing strut diameter. On the other hand, the specimens loaded in the Z- direction show a significantly low *YM* with 17 out of 24 values below or equal to 40 GPa. The *YM* value increases with increasing strut diameter. The only exception is the specimen FCCZ-0.55 with a *YM* of only 22 GPa at a strut diameter of 4.41 mm and FCCZ-0.7 with a *YM* of 40 GPa and a strut diameter of 5.51 mm. This could also be a local manufacturing defects.

These results indicate a material anisotropy that has never been observed in additively manufactured AlSi10Mg material, especially after heat treatment. The possible cause is discussed in the following Section 3.4.

Figure 6. Results of YM with linear trends and sorted by a) lattice topology, b) loading direction.

3.4. The anisotropy of the material

Authors who have studied the additively manufactured AISi10Mg material agree that, with the exception of ductility, the material is not prone to anisotropy, which is commonly observed in additive manufacturing thanks to layer-by-layer fabrication.^[9] Furthermore, the 6-hour solution treatment used should completely eliminate the influence of the layers and homogenize the material.^[36,37]

The specimens were randomly divided into two groups for the tests so that any influence of the fabrication, i.e. recoating problems, the flow of the protective atmosphere, the position on the platform with respect to the laser or the position in the furnace, should have been minimized and is very unlikely.

The condition of the material in terms of porosity could be a valid reason. According to the metallographic samples, the small-diameter Z-struts in the corners of the specimens had higher porosity values (0.58%) than the other struts (0.28%). Therefore, their load bearing capacity was lower. This was more significant when loading in the Z-direction, as the Z-struts did not significantly affect the performance of the specimens when loading in the XY-direction (Figure 3b and Figure 5b). However, Figure 6a shows that the anisotropy is present regardless of the Z-strut. A more general explanation must therefore be found.

The next possible explanation is the accuracy of fabrication and the deformed shape of the struts due to the partially melted powder on the underside of the struts, as reported by other authors.^[28,38] **Figure 7a**, showing the BCC-0.3 specimen, shows a partially melted powder on the underside of the struts. However, **Figure 7b**, which shows the vertical cross-section of the strut of the same specimen, indicates that the downward-facing surface contains partially

melted powder particles, but the shape is still circular. Furthermore, the typical elliptical shape with the major axis parallel to the Z-direction should increase the stiffness in the Z-direction, not otherwise. Finally, the authors report the significant deviations in strut shape for thinner struts. The diameters used in this study are usually reported to be free of significant defects.^[21,28]

Figure 7. BCC0.3 specimen a) front view, b) cross section of a strut.

The last possible explanation is the presence of internal stresses in the material caused by water cooling during the T6 treatment. As Vaverka et al. have shown, the internal stress is always present and directional,^[14] i.e. the water cooling has caused a preload in each sample that is directed towards the build platform. Assuming that the preload is constant across the platform, it should be more noticeable in the specimens with smaller strut diameters and especially affect the performance in the Z-direction. As the strut diameter increases, the effect should decrease and the loading in the Z- and XY-direction should become similar, as can be seen in Figure 6b for a strut diameter greater than approximately 3.5 mm.

3.5. Experimental comparison of mechanical performance of lattice types

In topology optimization, the required stiffness in a given region is defined by the reduced YM of the solid material (in this study, the EM of the structure is the same property) and is expressed by the value of the relative density calculated by some of the material interpolation schemes.^[42] This comparative study shows that the choice of lattice topology is a crucial factor for the geometric representation of the topology optimization results. The best results in terms of stiffness and uniaxial compressive loading should be obtained with the FCCZ topology.

The experimental tests show that up to 36% mass can be saved when loading in the Z-direction - the EM of the BFCC with a relative density of 0.55 is equal to the EM of the FCC at a relative density of about 0.35. In the XY-direction, the mass saving is 22% when the EM of BCCZ at a relative density of 0.55 is the same as that of FCCZ at a relative density of 0.43.

The specimen BFCCZ-0.7 was excluded from the comparison. These results again confirm the first hypothesis for the Z-direction, but not for the XY-direction.

Figure 8 shows the ratio of EM for the XY- and Z-directions from experimental tests, which was influenced by the observed load dependence. Only 13/24 specimens show higher or at least equal EM values when loaded in the Z-direction, which is in contrast to the FEA results with 19/24 specimens. The BCC specimens are also anisotropic in the experiments. On the other hand, the experimental tests confirmed the numerical results that the BFCC type is more suitable for loading in the XY-direction for the whole range of relative densities.

Therefore, the second hypothesis could not be generally confirmed and is limited to the FCC and BCCZ lattice types.

Figure 8. Ratio of EM for loading in Z- and XY-direction according to the experimental testing.

In the extreme case where the part consists of a BCCZ lattice structure with a relative density of 0.55 and is loaded in the XY-direction, the resulting EM of the structured material is approx. 10 GPa (FEA) or 7.5 GPa (experiment). Then, by changing the lattice topology, in this case FCCZ (FEA) or FCC (experiment) and changing the manufacturing orientation to change the load direction to Z-, the resulting relative density is approx. 0.3 (FEA) or approx. 0.37 (experiment) with the same EM value. This means a mass saving of 44.5% (FEA) or 32.7% (experiment) with the same stiffness of the structure.

4. Conclusion

This work dealt with the experimental and numerical evaluation of structured materials for use in multi-scale topology optimization. The aim was to compare different lattice types and to test two hypotheses, namely that a significant saving of mass while maintaining stiffness is

possible when changing the lattice topology for the geometric representation of the optimization results or when changing the fabrication orientation and thus the loading direction of an optimized part. Six truss-based lattice types with a relative density in the range of 0.3–0.7 were included in the study. The lattice topologies were subjected to finite element analysis and evaluated in two uniaxial loading directions. The lattice topologies were fabricated from AlSi10Mg material using Laser Powder Bed Fusion technology and heat treated to T6 condition for experimental comparison. The specimens were then subjected to compressive loading in the direction parallel to the build direction (Z-) and perpendicular to it (XY-).

The conclusions of this article can be summarized in points:

- The first hypothesis was confirmed for the Z-direction by FEA and by the experiments. The mass saving caused by the change of the lattice topology could reach up to 43% (FEA) or 36% (experiment). In the XY- direction, the mass saving was less than 30% (29% and 22% respectively).
- The second hypothesis could not be generally confirmed and is only limited to the FCC and BCCZ lattice types. For the other lattice types, the direction parallel to the build direction is not generally advantageous and depends on the relative density or is even generally not advantageous (BFCC topology).
- If both hypotheses are combined, the mass saving with constant stiffness is 44.5% (FEA) or 32.7% (experiment).
- In both loading directions, the FCC or FCCZ topologies achieved the highest values of the effective modulus of elasticity. On the other hand, the lowest values were obtained for the BCC topology.
- The experiments showed a significant anisotropic behavior of the specimens, independent of the lattice topology. The authors suggest that the anisotropy is caused by the inner stress induced by the water cooling during the T6 treatment.

The superiority of the FCC and FCCZ topologies has only been demonstrated for compressive loading. However, the real parts are rarely loaded in pure compression. Therefore, future work should focus on the comparison of the lattice topologies in shear, torsion and especially in mixed loading. Only through such a complex comparison can the suitability of the respective lattice topologies for real loading conditions be proven.

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